

out on a Philips digital pH-meter with a combined assembly of glass (PV 9011) and calomel (PV 9021) electrodes at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. Representative titration curves are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

The proton-ligand constants of KIMDA ($pK_1 = 9.05$), K_3 EDTA ($pK_1 = 9.26$), K_3 CDTA ($pK_1 = 11.22$), CCA ($pK_1 = 2.42$, $pK_2 = 5.88$), MIA ($pK_1 = 2.16$, $pK_2 = 6.03$), MLA ($pK_1 = 2.69$, $pK_2 = 5.75$), PHA ($pK_1 = 2.82$, $pK_2 = 5.35$), ODA ($pK_1 = 3.10$, $pK_2 = 4.18$), MEA ($pK_1 = 3.22$, $pK_2 = 4.72$) and TRA ($pK_1 = 2.71$, $pK_2 = 4.09$) were calculated by the method of Cheberek and Martell⁷. Formation constants of ternary and quaternary complexes were evaluated by the modified method⁴ of Ramamoorthy and Santappa⁸ for the simultaneous chelation of the ligands to form quaternary complexes. However, in the case of stepwise addition of the ligands to the metal ion the method of Thompson and Loraas⁹ was applied.

The relative order of the formation constants (Table 1) in terms of metal ions was $La^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Gd^{III} < Dy^{III}$. This could be corrected to the increasing polarisability of the metal ions due to the decreasing size and increasing ionic potential. Stability order for complexes in terms of dicarboxylic acids was $MIA < MLA < PHA$ and for hydroxy acids: $TRA < MEA$ due to the increased basicity of the ligands.

Considering the aminopolycarboxylic acids, the order of stability in terms of these acids has been observed as $EDTA < CDTA$, which may be explained on the basis of increased number of fused ring systems.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Prof. K. N. Mehrotra, Agra University and Dr. J. P. Tandon, Rajasthan University, for valuable suggestions. One of the authors (R.N.) is grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial support.

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Fungicidal Studies of Manganese(II), Iron(III), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of Schiff Bases derived from some Sulpha Drugs

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Manuscript received 25 April 1988, revised 19 April 1989, accepted 23 May 1989

METAL complexes^{1,2} play a vital role in metabolic and toxicological functions in the biological systems. The Schiff bases derived from sulpha drugs and salicylaldehyde have been successfully used as chelating agents³⁻⁶, bactericidal and fungicidal^{7,8} agents. The present paper describes the synthesis, characterisation and fungicidal studies of Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of Schiff bases derived from 5-nitro- and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde with sulphafurazole and sulphamethoxy pyridazine.

Experimental

5-Nitrosalicylaldehyde and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde were synthesised⁹ from salicylaldehyde (S. M.). The sulpha drugs were procured as reported earlier⁴. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade and double-distilled solvents were used throughout. The apparatus and techniques used were as reported earlier⁴.

The Schiff bases were synthesised by refluxing sulpha drug and 5-nitro- and 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde in ethanol in 1:1 ratio in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and a few drops of glacial acetic acid for 3-4 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into water and the product was crystallised from acetone.

All the metal complexes were isolated by reacting aqueous solution of metal ion (0.02 M) and acetone solution of Schiff base (0.02 M) in appropriate proportion. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3-4 h and the resulting coloured crystals were washed with water, crystallised from ethanol and dried in an oven ($110-20^\circ$).

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analysis (Table 1) reveal that the Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , and Cu^{II} complexes have 1:2 and the Fe^{II} complexes have 1:3 (M:L) stoichiometry.

The Schiff bases show broad ir bands at ~ 3420 cm^{-1} which is due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding involving hydrogen of the phenolic group and nitrogen atom of imine group^{10,11}. This band is absent in the spectra of the complexes indicating the replacement of phenolic hydrogen by metal ion and formation of M-O bond. Another notable

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF SCHIFF BASES AND METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					Metal	μ_{eff} B.M.
	C	H	N	S	OI		
DISHNBA	51.82 (51.92)	3.89 (3.85)	13.42 (13.46)	7.64 (7.69)	—	—	—
Mn(DISHNBA) ₂	48.98 (48.81)	3.31 (3.39)	12.72 (12.66)	7.20 (7.23)	—	6.17 (6.21)	5.80
Fe(DISHNBA) ₂	49.74 (49.81)	3.42 (3.46)	12.86 (12.91)	7.50 (7.58)	—	4.84 (4.30)	5.88
Co(DISHNBA) ₂	48.78 (48.60)	3.40 (3.37)	12.51 (12.60)	7.14 (7.20)	—	6.58 (6.63)	4.53
Ni(DISHNBA) ₂	48.78 (48.61)	3.40 (3.38)	12.43 (12.61)	7.32 (7.20)	—	6.64 (6.60)	—
Cu(DISHNBA) ₂	48.24 (48.37)	3.40 (3.35)	12.69 (12.53)	7.08 (7.16)	—	7.15 (7.11)	1.87
DISHOBA	53.38 (53.37)	3.82 (3.95)	10.28 (10.36)	7.94 (7.89)	8.81 (8.75)	—	—
Mn(DISHOBA) ₂	48.98 (50.04)	3.50 (3.47)	9.60 (9.72)	7.32 (7.41)	8.06 (8.22)	6.31 (6.36)	5.90
Fe(DISHOBA) ₂	50.98 (51.05)	3.60 (3.54)	9.97 (9.93)	7.60 (7.56)	8.42 (8.39)	4.36 (4.40)	5.90
Co(DISHOBA) ₂	49.98 (49.77)	3.40 (3.46)	9.61 (9.68)	7.42 (7.37)	8.24 (8.18)	6.82 (6.79)	4.52
Ni(DISHOBA) ₂	49.60 (49.79)	3.52 (3.46)	9.74 (9.68)	7.31 (7.37)	8.09 (8.18)	6.72 (6.77)	—
Cu(DISHOBA) ₂	49.70 (49.51)	3.33 (3.44)	9.70 (9.63)	7.30 (7.33)	8.30 (8.14)	7.32 (7.28)	1.89
MPSHNBA	50.52 (50.35)	3.46 (3.50)	16.38 (16.32)	7.50 (7.46)	—	—	—
Mn(MPSHNBA) ₂	47.50 (47.42)	3.12 (3.07)	16.26 (15.37)	7.12 (7.03)	—	5.98 (6.03)	5.88
Fe(MPSHNBA) ₂	48.24 (48.36)	3.08 (3.13)	15.79 (15.67)	7.23 (7.17)	—	4.19 (4.17)	5.94
Co(MPSHNBA) ₂	47.30 (47.22)	3.12 (3.06)	15.40 (15.30)	7.08 (7.00)	—	6.43 (6.44)	4.53
Ni(MPSHNBA) ₂	47.34 (47.23)	3.01 (3.06)	15.42 (15.30)	7.10 (7.00)	—	6.40 (6.42)	—
Cu(MPSHNBA) ₂	46.84 (46.98)	3.11 (3.05)	15.34 (15.22)	6.90 (6.96)	—	6.86 (6.91)	1.88
MPSHOBA	51.64 (51.52)	3.57 (3.60)	13.36 (13.28)	7.61 (7.65)	8.52 (8.48)	—	—
Mn(MPSHOBA) ₂	48.60 (48.54)	3.11 (3.15)	12.62 (12.59)	7.17 (7.19)	8.20 (7.98)	6.14 (6.17)	5.89
Fe(MPSHOBA) ₂	49.45 (49.52)	3.25 (3.21)	12.92 (12.84)	7.40 (7.34)	8.25 (8.14)	4.30 (4.27)	5.91
Co(MPSHOBA) ₂	48.40 (48.33)	3.09 (3.13)	12.54 (12.53)	7.20 (7.16)	7.87 (7.94)	6.56 (6.59)	4.53
Ni(MPSHOBA) ₂	48.37 (48.34)	3.15 (3.13)	12.58 (12.53)	7.11 (7.16)	7.95 (7.94)	6.62 (6.57)	—
Cu(MPSHOBA) ₂	48.12 (48.07)	3.13 (3.12)	12.50 (12.42)	7.00 (7.12)	7.94 (7.90)	7.11 (7.07)	1.88

*DISHNBA = 4-[5-(3,4-dimethylisooxazolyl)sulphamyl]-2'-hydroxy-5'-nitrobenzylidene aniline; DISHOBA = 4-[5-(3,4-dimethylisooxazolyl)sulphamyl]-2'-hydroxy-5'-chlorobenzylidene aniline; MPSHNBA = 4-[3-(6-methoxy)sulphamyl]-2'-hydroxy-5'-nitrobenzylidene aniline; MPSHOBA = 4-[3-(6-methoxy)sulphamyl]-2'-hydroxy-5'-chlorobenzylidene aniline.

change in ir spectra of the metal complexes is the appearance of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ band at $1625 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ as compared to $\sim 1640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the Schiff bases, thus showing a shift towards lower wave number by $10-20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This lowering indicates the coordination of nitrogen of imine group with the metal ion¹¹ (M-N bond). The strong ligand band at $\sim 1260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C-O) appeared at ~ 1300 in the complexes, showing a shift towards high wave number by $30-40 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This shift further supports the formation of M-O bond^{12,13}.

The metal complexes also showed some new bands of medium and low intensity at 580 ± 10

assignable to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ respectively. These bands may also be coupled with the ligand bands¹⁴.

Magnetic and electronic spectral data of the complexes reveal that the Fe^{III} complexes have high-spin octahedral geometry, the Mn^{II} and Co^{II} complexes have tetrahedral geometry while the complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} are square-planar.

Fungicidal studies: Growth method¹⁵ was employed for evaluating the fungitoxic effect against *Alternaria alternata*, *Curvularia lunata* and *Fusarium oxysporum* at 100, 50 and 20 ppm concentrations

TABLE 2—FUNGICIDAL DATA OF SCHIFF BASES AND METAL COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Average % inhibition (Concentration in ppm)								
	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>			<i>Curvularia lunata</i>			<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>		
	100	50	20	100	50	20	100	50	20
DISHNBA	30 44	20 52	11 72	38 64	25 73	14 34	32 70	21 92	12 84
Mn(DISHNBA) ₂	25 62	16 70	7 68	27 46	17 72	9 22	25 98	17 08	8 64
Fe(DISHNBA) ₂	25 50	16 54	7 52	27 20	17 50	9 08	25 80	16 86	8 50
Co(DISHNBA) ₂	25 80	16 88	7 94	27 68	18 04	9 48	26 70	17 32	8 86
Ni(DISHNBA) ₂	25 86	16 96	8 02	27 82	18 20	9 60	26 82	17 44	8 98
Cu(DISHNBA) ₂	26 02	17 14	8 24	28 58	18 76	10 12	27 14	17 84	9 22
DISHOBA	32 56	21 63	13 04	41 57	27 12	15 02	35 46	24 23	14 78
Mn(DISHOBA) ₂	26 42	16 94	8 20	30 95	18 64	9 78	26 49	17 84	9 37
Fe(DISHOBA) ₂	26 10	16 60	7 46	30 42	18 10	9 40	26 20	17 12	9 06
Co(DISHOBA) ₂	26 92	17 23	8 78	31 62	19 25	10 24	27 12	18 49	9 80
Ni(DISHOBA) ₂	27 14	17 41	8 94	31 78	19 32	10 35	27 30	18 85	9 88
Cu(DISHOBA) ₂	27 92	18 12	9 35	32 24	19 98	10 78	27 88	19 20	10 46
MPSHNBA	30 36	39 26	22 46	74 86	38 35	21 95	70 24	36 22	22 24
Mn(MPSHNBA) ₂	36 26	23 24	12 78	35 96	20 76	12 24	33 78	22 84	12 86
Fe(MPSHNBA) ₂	35 87	20 84	12 12	34 24	20 12	11 80	32 78	22 00	12 00
Co(MPSHNBA) ₂	39 02	24 22	13 62	37 02	22 79	13 86	34 60	23 30	13 30
Ni(MPSHNBA) ₂	39 20	24 40	13 84	37 12	23 06	13 62	34 89	23 42	13 42
Cu(MPSHNBA) ₂	40 84	25 87	14 79	38 54	24 12	14 14	35 76	24 02	14 02
MPSHOBA	34 68	41 54	24 32	79 23	40 67	23 56	75 46	40 02	23 12
Mn(MPSHOBA) ₂	38 57	24 78	13 24	37 82	23.46	13 12	35 80	23.00	13 20
Fe(MPSHOBA) ₂	38 12	24 23	12 95	37 46	22 98	12 81	35 44	22 12	12 78
Co(MPSHOBA) ₂	39 43	24 45	13 78	38 12	24 04	13 97	36 05	23 78	14 00
Ni(MPSHOBA) ₂	39 70	24 60	14 12	38 40	24 12	14 11	36 18	23 94	14 25
Cu(MPSHOBA) ₂	41 52	26 02	15 06	39 95	24 97	14 87	37 26	24 46	14 93

*Abbr same as in Table 1.

using Czapeck's Dox agar medium. Percentage inhibition¹⁶ was calculated (after 168 h).

The fungicidal screening data are presented in Table 2. The Schiff bases were found to be more fungitoxic than the metal complexes. The fungicidal activity showed a gradual change with change of metal ion in the complexes and revealed the order, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} > \text{Mn}^{\text{II}} > \text{Fe}^{\text{III}}$. Thus the Fe^{III} complexes were found to be least toxic while the Cu^{II} complexes showed maximum fungitoxicity. Generally, Schiff bases containing chloro group were found to be more fungitoxic than those containing nitro group. However, all the Schiff bases and their metal complexes were found to be fungitoxic although in varied degrees.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.G.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi for awarding a Teacher Fellowship.

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Polarographic Behaviour of DDD and BHC in Aqueous Mixtures of Organic Solvents and in Presence of some Ionic and Non-ionic Surfactants vis-a-vis Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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 Manuscript received 3 March 1987, revised 3 March 1989,
 accepted 4 May 1989

A survey of literature reveals that polarographic behaviour of DDD and BHC in aqueous mixtures of inert organic solvents and in the presence of ionic and non-ionic surfactants vis-a-vis kinetics of